

Implementation of One Stop Service at the Yogyakarta City Licensing Service in Improving the Investment Climate in the City of Yogyakarta in 2020

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ABSTRACT

One of the innovations built in order to provide the best service is the One Stop Service (PTSP) pattern or what is often called the One Stop Service (OSS). The City of Yogyakarta has a high commitment to increasing economic growth through improving the investment climate. This study aims to find out: 1) the implementation of OSS at the Yogyakarta City Licensing Service in improving the investment climate in 2020, 2) the factors that influence improving the investment climate in 2020. Data collection techniques used were interviews, document studies, and surveys of 50 respondents as OSS service users.

INTRODUCTION

One of the excellent service patterns that have been implemented by the regional government is one stop service, namely a one-stop integrated service pattern held in one place covering various types of services that have process linkages and are served through various doors. The one-stop integrated service pattern is aimed at providing service convenience to the community, the community only needs to come to one place to get service, and there is no need to go to the service or licensing agencies whose locations are spread out (Hardiyansyah, 2011).

Regarding licensing services, the City of Yogyakarta has a One-Stop Service Office (PTSP) as an institution specifically tasked with providing direct licensing services to the public. The PTSP can be said to be a new breakthrough or innovation in government management in the regions, especially in the City of Yogyakarta. This policy is in line with the implementation of regional autonomy, so the Yogyakarta City Government is trying to encourage economic growth through improving the investment climate by paying greater attention to the role of micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs).

The city of Yogyakarta received the first ranking award from the International Finance Corporation (IFC) in 2012 as the best city in terms of ease of starting a business. In addition to the category for ease of starting a business, the City of Yogyakarta was ranked fifth in the category of dealing with Building Permits (IMB), while in the category of property transfers it was ranked sixth. The survey results from the International Finance Corporation (IFC) can be a reference for investors to be able to invest in the City of Yogyakarta (Syahputri, 2012).

The award obtained is inseparable from the role of the Yogyakarta City Licensing Service as an agency in the field of services, especially in terms of licensing, because licensing is an important aspect of public service, as well as licensing related to business activities. The licensing process, especially business licensing, will directly affect the wishes and decisions of prospective entrepreneurs and investors to invest their capital. Vice versa, if the licensing process is inefficient, convoluted, and not transparent both in terms of time, costs, and procedures, it will have an impact on reducing the desire of investors to take care of business licensing, and investors will look for other investment places where the process is clearer and more transparent. .

The economic sector in the city of Yogyakarta still relies heavily on secondary and tertiary sectors such as manufacturing, trade, hotels, restaurants, transportation, telecommunications, finance, leasing, corporate services and others where in practice business actors really need investment information and licensing. Besides that, the Yogyakarta City government is also committed to increasing investment, both through policies, programs, and ease of licensing for investors. Investment is one of the most important economic driving mottos because investment is able to increase the added value of economic activity so that economic growth will occur, increase employment opportunities and improve people's welfare.

IMPLEMENTATION AND METHODS

The research method used is a qualitative descriptive research method because it is to provide an overview of the implementation of One Stop Service at the Yogyakarta City Licensing Service in improving the investment climate in the City of Yogyakarta in 2020. The research location is in the Yogyakarta City Licensing Service considering that this service has implemented a one-stop integrated licensing service. Data collection techniques used are interviews, document studies, and surveys. The stages include data collection, data reduction, data presentation, as well as drawing conclusions and verification (Taufiq Efendi, 2012).

Picture 1. Conceptual Framework

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

- a. Implementation of One Stop Service at the Yogyakarta City Licensing Service in Improving the Investment Climate in the City of Yogyakarta in 2020.

Knowing the implementation of One Stop Service (OSS) at the Yogyakarta City Licensing Service in improving the investment climate used an index scale by conducting a survey of 50 respondents as users of OSS services. (Dwiyanto, 2008) the service indicators used are as follows:

1. Tangible (visible/tangible), this indicator describes the physical appearance of buildings, equipment, employees, and other facilities owned by providers. Based on the results of the analysis of the respondent's assessment, it was explained that the tangible indicators consisted of dimensions: 1) ease of procedure/stages of the service flow, 2) presence of service personnel, 3) discipline of service personnel, 4) convenience of service places and 5) security of service places. From these five dimensions, the community assesses the tangible indicators as good, some even say that it is very good related

to the presence of service officers in providing services to the community.

2. Reliability, this indicator describes the ability to perform the promised service accurately. Based on the results of the analysis of the respondent's assessment, the reliability indicators were explained, which consisted of the following dimensions: 1) the accuracy of service personnel and 2) the responsibility of service personnel. From these two dimensions, the community assesses the reliability indicator as good in providing services to the community.
3. Responsiveness (response/responsiveness), this indicator explains the willingness of service officers to help consumers be responsible for the quality of services provided. Based on the results of the analysis of the respondent's assessment, the responsiveness indicators were explained which consisted of dimensions: 1) service speed, and 2) all complaints were responded to by officers. From these two dimensions it can be concluded that the responsiveness indicator is good in providing services to the community.
4. Assurance (guarantee), this indicator explains the ability of service officers to give trust to the people who receive services. Based on the results of the analysis of the respondent's assessment, the assurance indicators consist of dimensions: 1) the certainty of the service schedule, and 2) the amount of fees set. From these two dimensions, it can be concluded that the assurance indicator is good, some even say it is very good in terms of service schedule certainty.
5. Empathy (attention), this indicator describes the treatment or personal attention given by service workers to the community. Based on the results of the analysis of the respondent's assessment, the empathy indicators were explained which consisted of dimensions: 1) friendliness and courtesy of officers and 2) fairness of service personnel. From these two dimensions, it can be concluded that the empathy indicator is good, especially in the fairness of service officers who do not look at social status in providing services.

Of the five indicators, after calculating the One Stop Service index scale at the Yogyakarta City Licensing Service in improving the investment climate, they are as follows:

Table. 1 One Stop Service Index Value

Variable Index	Index Value Element
Ease of service procedures	3,10
The presence of service officers	3,86
Officer discipline	3,18
Convenience of service places	3,26
Security place of service	3,10
Accuracy of service personnel	3,10
Responsibilities of service officers	3,14
Capability (expertise and skill)	3,30
Service speed	3,12
Officers responded to all complaints	3,14
Certainty of service schedule	3,84
The fairness of the amount of levy	3,04
Friendliness and courtesy	3,10
Fairness of service officers	3,16
Service Index	3,26
The value of IKM after being converted	81,43

Source: Primary Data Processing, 2020.

Based on the table and graph above, it shows that each indicator in the implementation of the One Stop Service at the Yogyakarta City Licensing Service in improving the investment climate is very good, with an average service index value of 3.26. Then it is shown by the IKM value after conversion, which is 81.43. Thus it can be concluded that the implementation of the One Stop Service at the Yogyakarta City Licensing Service in improving the investment climate in the City of Yogyakarta in 2020 has entered the category of Very Good service work units with service quality (A).

b. Factors Influencing the Improvement of the Investment Climate in the City of Yogyakarta in 2020

Improving the investment climate in 2020 is highly dependent on the role of the Yogyakarta City Licensing Service, because licensing is an important aspect of public service, as well as licensing related to business activities. An investor will first see the licensing process, if the licensing is effective and efficient then the investor will be interested in investing in the City of Yogyakarta. In improving the investment climate in the City of Yogyakarta, there are factors that will influence the improvement of the investment climate in the City of Yogyakarta in 2020, namely:

1. Availability of Fast and Accurate Investment Information

In supporting investment policies in the City of Yogyakarta, the Licensing Office of the City of Yogyakarta has formed an Investment and Advice Planning Outlet which is tasked with providing information services regarding investments. The Investment Outlet is an investment or investment information service unit, the public can ask all questions

regarding investment, starting from the requirements, type of business, and locations or areas that have potential for investment. Meanwhile, Advice Planning is tasked with providing information and input which includes: consulting on the design and location of buildings in accordance with the Spatial and Regional Spatial Plans of the City of Yogyakarta.

The availability of fast and accurate investment information, this fast investment information indicator can be proven by the hits of investment website visitors in the City of Yogyakarta, because prospective investors or the public do not need to come to the Yogyakarta City Licensing Service to obtain all information regarding investments in the City of Yogyakarta, the community only needs to stay visit the Investment website at the portal. With this website, the public can find out all investment opportunities in the City of Yogyakarta, starting from investment permit procedures, information requirements, types of businesses, locations or areas that have potential for investment (DPMPTSP DIY, 2011).

2. Ease of Investment Procedures

The investment procedure in the City of Yogyakarta is very easy, that is, investors only need to come to the Licensing Office of the City of Yogyakarta, then they will be directed to the Investment Outlet which will provide information regarding the investment, then they will be directed to the Advice Planning which will provide an overview of the design and location of the investment building to be will be built. After the Advice Planning, the prospective investor is ready to carry out investment activities. The ease of investment procedures at the Yogyakarta City Licensing Service has had a huge impact on improving the investment climate in the City of Yogyakarta in 2020 as shown by an increase in the number of applicants by 4591 applicants and the number of permits issued as many as 5032 permits issued, especially in business licensing which includes: Building Permits (IMB), Nuisance Permit (HO), Trading Business Permit (SIUP), and Company Registration Certificate (TDP).

3. Investor Satisfaction

Investor satisfaction in the investment licensing process at the Yogyakarta City Licensing Service is very well indicated by the IKM (Community Satisfaction Index) for Very Good licensing services (A) with a conversion interval value of 83.79. Then to increase the satisfaction of the business community in investment activities, the City of Yogyakarta provides investment incentives to potential investors, namely by providing reductions or relief and exemption from IMB Retribution and Interference Permits (HO).

4. Investment Growth Rate

In an effort to attract investment activities, the Yogyakarta City government is committed to improving the investment climate in 2020, both through policies, programs and ease of licensing at the Yogyakarta

City Licensing Service. In improving the investment climate, the Yogyakarta City Licensing Service made several innovations in encouraging the growth of the investment climate in the City of Yogyakarta, namely by establishing Investment and Advice Planning Outlets that function to provide information regarding investments to investors. This innovation has an impact on the average economic growth rate for the City of Yogyakarta during 2019-2020 which reached 4.69%. A figure that is higher than the average growth rate for the province of DIY, which only reached 4.56%.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of the analysis of the data obtained during the research, it can be concluded that the implementation of the One Stop Service at the Yogyakarta City Licensing Service has been very good in efforts to improve the investment climate in the Yogyakarta City, this is due to licensing services, especially business permits at the Yogyakarta City Licensing Service. not convoluted, transparent, has certainty of time and certainty of costs, so that potential investors or investors are interested in investing in the City of Yogyakarta which will have an impact on economic growth in the City of Yogyakarta.

REFERENCES

- DPMPTSP DIY. (2011). Dinas Penanaman Modal dan Pelayanan Terpadu Satu Pintu DIY. DPMPTSP DIY. Retrieved from <https://jogjainvest.jogjaprovo.go.id/web/>
- Dwiyanto, A. (2008). Mewujudkan Good Governance Melalui Pelayanan Publik. Yogyakarta: Gadjah Mada University Press.
- Hardiyansyah. (2011). Kualitas Pelayanan Publik, Konsep, Dimensi, Indikator, Dan Implementasinya. Yogyakarta: Gaya Media.
- Syahputri, E. (2012). Yogya kota terbaik termudah mendirikan usaha. Antaranews.Com.
- Taufiq Efendi. (2012). Reformasi Birokrasi dan Iklim Investasi. Jakarta: Konpres.